

**MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS
AT SCHOOL BASED ON A CREATIVE APPROACH**

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of managing the creative process. The contradictions that arise in connection with the current state of education, requiring the creativity of education, are highlighted. Creativity is considered as the ability to combine all kinds of elements of existing experience and knowledge into new formations. Because of this, in a modern university it is necessary to go beyond the understanding of learning as a process of transferring ready-made knowledge and accumulating a certain amount of information.

Key words: creativity, creative environment, creative motivation, creative process management, creative education.

Introduction. The changes taking place in modern society in general and education in particular lead to the fact that the problem of the relationship between personality traits and creativity not only does not lose its relevance, but also leads to the need to identify new facets of this process [4, 6, 7]. Today, higher education can rightfully be considered the most important resource for innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1, 2]. The knowledge and creative potential of workers become the main factor in the efficiency of the economic system, without which its technical and economic progress is unattainable, regardless of the amount of funds invested in production equipment and technologies [3, 5].

Not only individuals, but also entire organizations strive to adapt to those changes in society that, at the global level, lead to changes in ideology, technology,

and goals. And in this situation, managing the creative process at a practical level can be considered an important element of success in any endeavor [8, 10, 11].

If we talk about the so-called “nature” of creativity, we should not forget that creativity does not have a nature, that it is not inherent to a person from birth [9, 12]. The kind of creativity we are considering remains a hypothetical construct that describes or explains a particular kind of specific human potential or ability. Creativity is not energy in itself, it is an inherent human potential associated with the personality, dependent on it and manifested in thinking and activity. This specific human activity leads to the emergence of a new, innovative product [4, 13].

There is an opinion that creativity is something similar to a gift. Such a point of view, undoubtedly, would not allow us to consider this personality trait in development. Creativity tends to be individualized [14, 15, 17]. Everyone strives to comprehend it on their own, looking for their own path, choosing methods and techniques. Often the moment of creativity cannot be formalized, and in many cases, most creative people have no idea about the strategies with which they create [16]. That is why managing the creative process raises many questions that have no answer yet. On the other hand, it is known that the criterion that we have learned to do something is the understanding that we have ceased to be aware of how we do it. To determine the level of creativity, J. Guilford identified 16 hypothetical intellectual abilities that characterize creativity. These are fluency and flexibility of thought, originality, curiosity, the ability to develop a hypothesis, unreality, fantasticness, the ability to solve problems, that is, the ability to analyze and synthesize, the ability to improve an object by adding details, and so on. They also identified four main parameters of creativity:

- originality - the ability to produce distant associations, unusual answers;
- semantic flexibility - the ability to highlight the function of an object and suggest its new use;
- figurative adaptive flexibility - the ability to change the shape of a stimulus in such a way as to see in it new signs and opportunities for use;

- semantic spontaneous flexibility - the ability to produce a variety of ideas in an unregulated situation [7, 19].

He also identifies the following indicators of creative thinking:

- speed and smoothness of the emergence of unusual associative connections;
- “susceptibility” to the problem;
- fluency of thought as the number of associations and ideas that arise per unit of time in accordance with a certain requirement;
- the ability to find new unusual functions of an object or its part [4, 20].

But the opinion of E. P. Torres does not completely coincide with the opinion of J. Guilford. He characterizes creativity by the following parameters:

- ease - speed of completing text tasks;
- flexibility - the number of switches from one class of objects to another during responses;
- originality - the minimum frequency of a given answer to a homogeneous group;
- accuracy of task completion [3, 21].

According to the law of requisite variety, we must constantly vary the actions and processes we use to achieve our goals. Even processes that have proven effective in the past may become less effective due to changes in the environment or external system. In other words, past success is one of the “traps” or limiters for creativity [22]. It is obvious that a successful method will probably retain its significance and effectiveness in the future.

However, as a result of changes in the surrounding system, previously effective methods can often no longer work. It is this fact that allows us to say that creativity is a necessary and continuous process. In particular, the Law of Requisite Variety emphasizes that “in order to successfully adapt to the world and survive, an element of a system needs a certain minimum amount of flexibility, and this flexibility must be proportional to the potential change or uncertainty of the rest of the system”.

A paradoxical situation arises in which, in order to create a truly new, creative product, you need to learn something that has not been new for a long time. But while nothing can guarantee creativity, it can be said, however, that a sufficient level of knowledge and skills significantly increases the likelihood of being able to combine individual elements into something original, something that will meet the main requirements for a creative product, novelty and significance.

It is obvious that the success of a modern graduate largely depends on the ability to generate creative ideas, since a developing society needs educated, moral, enterprising people who can independently make responsible decisions in a situation of choice, predicting their possible consequences, are capable of cooperation, are creative, and mobile. , dynamism and constructiveness.

Thus, creativity is presented as the ability to combine all kinds of elements of existing experience and knowledge into new formations. At the same time, a person's endless ability to associate allows him to generate any required number of ideas.

Currently, the basic principles of creativity pedagogy have been updated:

- recognition of previously unrecognized or unexploited opportunities;
- respect for the student's desire to work independently;
- the ability to refrain from interfering in the process of creative activity;
- providing the student with freedom to choose the area of application of forces and methods of achieving the goal;
- individual application of the curriculum depending on the characteristics of the students;
- creating conditions for the concrete implementation of ideas;
- providing opportunities to contribute to the common cause of the group;
- encouraging work on projects proposed by the students themselves;
- eliminating any pressure on students;
- emphasizing the positive meaning of individual differences;
- respect for the potential capabilities of those lagging behind;

- demonstration of enthusiasm;
- creating situations in which more successful students work with weaker students;
- search for possible points of contact between the ideal and the real;
- approval of the results of students' activities in any area in order to encourage a desire to test themselves in other types of activities;
- providing authoritative assistance to students who express a different opinion from others and are under pressure from their peers.

Taking this into account, we can conclude that in order to form and develop creativity as a personal quality of a future specialist, it is necessary to create conditions for students to master the following skills - projective, heuristic, intellectual and research. At certain stages of mastering the content of academic disciplines, these skills have an independent status and can be formed and developed in separate components or blocks. In general, generalized skills are interdependent in nature, the level of formation of these skills in a modern specialist determines his awareness, skill in specific creativity, the ability to assimilate information coming from outside and contributes to the acquisition of experience in independent creative and cognitive activity. And in this case we can talk about creative education.

In creative education, the most comprehensive and effective method is learning by action, which is carried out in the form of solving real professional problems, analyzing and playing out specific situations, joint activities of a study group, and independent work.

The role of active learning is significantly increasing, in which the student is not a passive listener, assimilating and repeating, but an active creator of knowledge and decisions, shaping his professional behavior. The most important place in the educational process should be given to independent work - a means of developing independence as a personal characteristic of a future specialist, increasing his cognitive, social and professional mobility, creating in him an actively transformative attitude towards the surrounding reality and towards himself.

Conclusions. The renewal of the modern education system, associated with the humanization of the educational process, necessitates pedagogical conditions that ensure the development of the creative abilities of each participant in the educational process. In this regard, the organization of pedagogical support aimed at creating a creative environment in an educational institution is of particular importance. It is built around the interests of students and performs the function of adapting the educational environment to their individual characteristics and subjective needs.

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